

PULLETS ACCESS TO LITTER FOR DUSTBATHING

Provision of litter is needed for **exploratory, playing and foraging behaviours** and **comfort** in general, specifically for **dustbathing**.

DUSTBATHING is recognized as a **behavioural need**.

Removing excess of lipids by dustbathing is critical for **preserving the thermoregulatory properties of the plumage**.

Poultry are **highly motivated** to perform dustbathing, specifically with substrates with small particle size such as peat or sand.

FROM WHEN SHOULD PULLETS HAVE ACCESS TO SUITABLE LITTER?

Pullets should have access to appropriate, dry and friable substrate from **DAY 1** until departure.

Necessary to ensure acceptance of substrate!

If not present shortly after hatching, proper development of dustbathing behavior **may not occur** (even later).

CONSEQUENCES OF DISRUPTED DUSTBATHING OR ABSENCE OF LITTER

FEATHER PECKING OR CANNIBALISM

May develop as redirected dustbathing behaviour in the absence of suitable litter.

NEGATIVE IMPACT ON WELFARE

Inability to perform dustbathing can lead to frustration, discomfort and stress.

FEATHER DAMAGE

Sham dustbathing (dustbathing even in the absence of litter) could lead to feather damage due to contact with abrasive surfaces (wire cages or concrete).

For any questions or suggestions regarding this document, please contact

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